

A STUDY OF RELATION BETWEEN ANXIETY AND ACHIEVEMENT MOTIVATION AMONG YOUTH

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Abstract

Conducted study on Anxiety and Achievement motivation among youth in Shirur city. Simple random sampling method for used data collection. Main purpose of the correlation in Anxiety and Achievement motivation youth boys and to see the correlation in Anxiety and Achievement motivation of youth girls. Eighty youth selected for this study. The data was obtained using Sinha's comprehensive Anxiety Test (SCAT): A. K. P. Sinha and L. N. K. Sinha and Achievement motivation scale: Pratibha Deo and Asha Mohan. The finding the prediction of There is positive correlation between anxiety and achievement motivation of youth boys and there is negative correlation between anxiety and achievement motivation of youth girls.

Keywords- *Anxiety, Achievement Motivation and youth.*

Introduction:

"The Youth of today are the nation of tomorrow" is an old saying but of immense significance for a country like Indian which has only recently emancipated itself from the subjugation of British. Today all people in higher positions in government and non-government sector thought that the future of India lies in the hands of the youth and would depend on their abilities and positive attitude towards own life and others life.

Youth development support young people in developing a sense of competence, usefulness, belongingness and empowerment. Youth development work best when entire communities including youths are involved. It creates a services and opportunities to youths for fulfilling their needs to grow into happy and healthy adults.

Anxiety

Anxiety is associated with specific brain circuits and neurotransmitter systems. According to American Psychiatric Association in 1994; and Barlow, in 2002, Anxiety is a negative mood state characterized by bodily symptoms of physical tension and apprehension about the future. In relation to stated that Barlow,2000,2002; Barlow,Chorpita & Turovsky, 1996; Mineka, Watson & Clark in 1998; Anxiety is closely related to depression.

"Anxiety is mood state characterized by marked negative affect and bodily symptoms of tension in which a person apprehensively anticipates future danger or misfortune. Anxiety may involve feelings,

behavior, and physiological responses.”

The main characteristic of generalized anxiety disorder is a persistent sense of “free-floating” anxiety, meaning that it follows the individual wherever they go. People who are chronically anxious can’t say what they are afraid of all they know is that they feel on edge most of the time. They generally worry a lot, anticipate that something bad is going to happen, and find it hard to concentrate or make decisions.

Achievement motivation

Achievement motivation can, therefore, be defined as the striving to increase or to keep as high as possible, one’s own capabilities in all activities in which a standard of excellence is thought to apply and where the execution of such activities can, therefore either succeed or fail.

Need for achievement refers to an individual’s desire for significant accomplishment, mastering of skills, control, or high standards. This personality trait is characterized by an enduring and consistent concern with setting and meeting high standards of achievement. This need is influenced by internal drive for action and the pressure exerted by the expectations of others.

Do individual differences in achievement and power motivation really matter? In other words, do persons high and low in these motives have contrasting life experiences? Existing evidence suggests that they do. As you might expect, individuals high in achievement motivation tend to get higher grades in school, earn more rapid promotions, and attain greater success in running their own businesses than persons low in such motivation (Raynor, 1970).

Achievement motivation seems to vary from person to person. Some people have high achievement motivations in school, while others in bowling, while others in nothing at all. What makes us strive for that goal-well one easy way to think about it is through extrinsic and intrinsic motivators. Achievement motivation typically refers to the level of one’s motivation to engage in achievement behaviors, based on the interaction of such parameters as need for achievement, expectancy of success, and the incentive value of success. Our construct of motivational orientation refers to the type of motivational stance which the child adopts toward classroom learning. Thus, one may engage in schoolwork for intrinsic reasons, because work is challenging, enjoyable, and piques one’s curiosity, or alternatively, one may engage in schoolwork for extrinsic reasons, either to obtain external approval or because the educational system requires it.

Objectives of the Study:

1. To study the correlation in Anxiety and achievement motivation of boys.
2. To see the correlation in Anxiety and achievement motivation of girls.

Hypothesis of the Study:

1. There is positive correlation between anxiety and achievement motivation of boys.
2. There is no correlation between anxiety and achievement motivation of girls.

Variables of the study:

In this present study boys and girls’ youth are independent variables and anxiety and achievement

motivation are dependent variables.

Sample of the study:-

In the present study, researcher has selected 80 samples, boys (40) and girls (40). Sample was select from Shirur city. Simple random sampling method for used for data collection.

Tools of the Study:-

Following tools was be used for the collection of the data.

Sinha's comprehensive Anxiety Test (SCAT): A. K. P. Sinha and L. N. K. Sinha

Achievement motivation scale: Pratibha Deo and Asha Mohan.

Results and Interpretation the Data was collected by administering the state and anxiety questionnaire and Achievement motivation inventory. The data thus collected was scored as per manual instruction and same is presented.

Table No.1

	Boys	Girls	Mean of Means
Anxiety	40.53	42.70	41.61
Achievement Motivation	20.43	22.80	21.61

In the table no.1 it is observed that the mean value of the youth boy in anxiety is 40.53, and there with mean value of the girls in anxiety is 42.70 and total mean of means is 41.61 on the other hand mean value of the youth girl in achievement motivation is 20.43 and there with mean value of the adolescents girls in achievement motivation is 22.80 and total mean of means is 21.61.

Table No.2

Group	Boys	Girls
Correlation	0.3146	-0.109

Conclusion:

1. There is positive correlation between anxiety and achievement motivation of youth boys
2. There is negative correlation between anxiety and achievement motivation of youth girls.

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